

A NOVEL MULTI-FUNCTIONAL SENSOR DESIGN FOR PROCESS MONITORING

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SUMMARY

This paper reports on a novel fibre optic sensor that is capable of monitoring four independent parameters: strain, temperature, refractive index and the relative concentrations of specific chemical species. A unique feature of this sensor is that a conventional fibre-coupled Fourier transform infrared spectrometer is used to interrogate the sensor.

Keywords: Fibre optic sensor, Temperature, Strain, Refractive index, Chemical sensing

INTRODUCTION

A wide range of optical fibre-based sensor systems have been developed and used for monitoring cross-linking reactions involving thermosetting resins [1]. However, the majority of these sensors generally impart information on a single parameter. For example, strain [2], temperature [3], refractive index [4] or the relative concentrations of specific functional groups in the resin system [5].

During cross-linking reactions involving thermosets, in addition to chemical reactions that result in the consumption of reactive functional groups, the reactions are exothermic. Therefore, thermal management is an important factor especially when thick components are processed. High-performance composites are generally processed between 120-180 °C. When the composite is cooled down to ambient temperature from the processing temperature, residual stresses develop in the composite due to a mismatch in the thermal expansion between the fibres and the matrix [6-8]. Furthermore, the cross-linking reactions also result in shrinkage [9]. Hence, there is significant merit in monitoring simultaneously the cross-linking kinetics, residual fabrication strain and temperature during processing.

Previous researchers have attempted to design multi-functional sensors but with limited functionality [10-13].

This paper reports on a new integrated fibre optic sensor design that can monitor simultaneously four independent parameters, namely, refractive index, strain, temperature and the concentrations of specified chemical functional groups via transmission infrared spectroscopy. The multi-functional sensor design is based on the conventional extrinsic fibre Fabry-Perot interferometer. A unique feature of the current sensor design is that the four measurands are interrogated simultaneously using a conventional fibre-coupled Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sensor Design

With reference to Figure 1, the basic sensor design is based on a conventional extrinsic fibre Fabry-Perot interferometric (EFPI) sensor. A precision-bore capillary tube [A] with internal and external diameters of 128 and 300 μm respectively is used to house cleaved primary optical fibres [B and B']; the cavity between the end-faces [C] of the cleaved optical fibre represents the primary Fabry-Perot cavity. The cleaved fibre is secured to the capillary via two fusion joints [D and D'].

The elements that transform the primary EFPI sensor into the 'multi-functional sensor' (MFS) are: (i) the reflective coating on the end-face of the capillary [F]; (ii) the secondary optical fibres [G, G' and G''] that are located and secured around the primary optical fibre [B']. The secondary optical fibres are arranged and secured in position to create secondary cavities [H]. The secondary optical fibres can be single- or multi-mode depending on the intended sensing application. For example, the secondary fibres [G and G''] illustrated in Figure 1 are multi-mode optical fibres and the cavity between the cleaved end-faces and the reflective coating serves as a 'cell' for conducting transmission/reflection near-infrared spectroscopy of the resin; the spectra can be used to extract quantitative data on the cross-linking kinetics of the thermosetting resin system.

With regard to qualitative process monitoring, cleaved secondary fibre(s) [G'] can be attached at a suitable distance away from the reflective coating of the capillary end-face to serve as Fresnel reflection-based refractive index sensors. Fibre Bragg gratings (FBG) [I] can be inscribed on the secondary fibres [for example G'] to enable the combined effects of strain and temperature to be monitored. The Bragg grating [E] on the primary optical fibre is in a strain-free condition and thus responds only to temperature [16]. Since the gauge length of the EFPI sensor is known (distance between the two fusion joints ([D] and [D'])), any changes in the cavity length [C] will enable the strain to be calculated.

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the multi-functional fibre optic sensor design.

Sensor Fabrication

Details of the fabrication procedures for the EFPI and multi-functional sensors were reported previously [14] and only a brief summary is presented here.

EFPI sensor: The conventional EFPI sensor consists of a cleaved optical fibre that is secured within a precision-bore capillary tube. The cleaved fibre is secured to the capillary tube via two fusion joints. The gap between the cleaved fibres represents the Fabry-Perot cavity. The gauge length is defined as the distance between the fusion joints.

MFS: In the multi-functional sensor design, the precision-bore capillary tube is used to house the cleaved optical fibres but in addition, the end-faces of the capillary are used as a reflective surface. Fused silica precision-bore capillaries with internal and external diameters of 128 and 300 μm respectively were potted into 1 mm bore SMA fibre connectors using a high-viscosity adhesive (2-component Araldite[®] rapid, Bostik Ltd., UK). A sacrificial optical fibre was inserted into the precision bore capillary tube prior to potting in order to offer mechanical stability and reduce contaminant ingress into the capillary during polishing.

The connectors were polished using a Senko APC8000 high-volume fibre-optic connector polisher. The polished capillaries were de-mounted from the connector by burning off the adhesive in a furnace. This capillary was then cleaned with iso-propanol in an ultrasonic bath. The polished end of the capillary was sputter-coated with gold using an Emscope SC500A gold coater at 27.5 mV for 4 minutes. During this operation, the bore of the capillary was protected using a sacrificial optical fibre. Germania-Boron (Ge-B) co-doped single-mode fibre (PS1250/1500, Fibercore Ltd., UK) was used for fabricating the primary Fabry-Perot cavity.

FBG sensors: Bragg gratings were inscribed in the Ge-B co-doped primary optical fibre using the phase-mask technique and an excimer laser (Braggstar, Coherent, UK) operating at 248 nm. The Bragg gratings were produced using a pulse energy of 10 mJ and 1500 pulses. The fibre with the Bragg grating was cleaved ensuring that the grating was located close to the cleaved-end.

Fresnel sensor: The Fresnel sensor consisted of a 2 x 2 custom-made coupler where the distal ends were cleaved. The coupler was constructed using a pair of multi-mode optical fibres (105/125 μm step-index silica core and fluorine-doped silica cladding, Aomolin Ltd, China). The cleaved fibre-ends were located 5 mm from the gold-coated capillary end-face. The Fresnel sensor (cleaved fibres) was attached to the primary optical fibre using a similar procedure to that described previously. The Fresnel sensor was connected to the FTIR spectrometer via the 2 x 2 coupler where the input arms were connected to the light-source and detector. In this instance, the intensity of the reflected light from the cleaved fibre was monitored using the FTIR spectrometer.

Conventional FTIR Spectroscopy and MFS Interrogation During Cross-linking

Resin system: The resin system used was LY3505 epoxy resin and XB3403 amine-based hardener (Huntsman Advanced Materials, UK). The resin and the hardener were mixed in the ratio of 100:35 by weight, followed by degassing in a vacuum chamber for 15 minutes. The mixed resin was transferred to the demountable cuvette (with the multi-functional sensor secured inside) via a syringe, and placed in a temperature-controlled cuvette holder (TLC50F, Ocean Optics, UK). The resin system was cured isothermally at 60 °C for 8 hours.

Resin and sensor containment: The cross-linking experiments were carried out using a de-mountable 1 mm path-length cuvette (Starna Scientific Ltd, UK). The multi-functional sensor was secured to an internal side-wall of the demountable cuvette using a UV-curable resin (UV 304-T). Conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy and the experiments involving the multi-functional sensor were carried out simultaneously.

Interrogation of the MFS and conventional FTIR spectroscopy: A schematic illustration of the experimental setup that was used to interrogate the multi-functional sensor and for conducting conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy is illustrated in Figure 2. The primary Fabry-Perot cavity was illuminated using an ASE light source emitting in the range of 1450-1600 nm. With reference to Figure 2, a commercially-available near-infrared transmitting fibre optic probe [i] was connected to one of the light output channels of the spectrometer and the other end was attached to a temperature-controlled cuvette holder (TLC 50F, Ocean Optics) [ii] via collimating optics [iii]. The light was transmitted from [iii] through the cuvette [iv] and the mixed resin [v], and was collected via collimating optics [iii'] and returned to a detector port on the spectrometer. Due care was taken to ensure that the sensor [vi] did not obstruct the light-path of the conventional transmission experiment. The secondary cavity for monitoring the cross-linking reactions and the Fresnel-based (refractive index) sensors, [vii] and [viii], respectively, were connected to the spectrometer via individual multi-mode 2x2 couplers [ix]. The redundant output arm of the coupler [x] was immersed in an index-matching gel. A K-type thermocouple [xi] was used to monitor the temperature of the mixed resin during cross-linking reaction. The unused channels on the spectrometer are indicated [xii]; two further sensor configurations can be added if required (evanescent wave spectroscopy, pH, multiplexed strain, etc).

Figure 2 Schematic illustration of the experimental set for conducting conventional FTIR spectroscopy and the interrogation system for the multi-functional sensor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Monitoring the Cross-linking Process

The evolution of FTIR spectra during the cross-linking of the LY3505 and XB3403 resin system using conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy and the multi-functional optical fibre sensors with a secondary cavity of 250 μm are presented in Figures 3(a and b) respectively. The resin system was cross-linked at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for eight hours using the temperature-regulated cuvette holder.

The combination band of the overtone of the C-H stretching and the deformation vibration associated with the epoxy ring at 2207 nm are readily apparent in Figures 2(a and b) [15-18]. The combination bands corresponding to stretching and bending vibrations of the primary amine ($-\text{NH}_2$) at 2025 nm [15-18] are also present. On comparing Figures 3(a and b), it is clear that the absorbance peaks of interest are similar for the two cases.

Figures 3(a and b) Spectral evolution during cure of epoxy/amine system at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The spectra were obtained using: (a) conventional FTIR spectroscopy in conjunction with a 1-mm part-length cuvette. (b) a secondary cavity on the multi-functional sensor. The circled numbers on the spectra are 1 = epoxy peak at 2207 nm, 2 = non-reacting aromatic CH peak at 2164 nm and 3 = primary amine peak at 2025 nm.

With reference to Figures 3(a and b), the depletion of the amine and epoxy functional groups is seen clearly as the cross-linking reaction proceeded.

The absorbance data for the epoxy and amine bands were normalised to an inert absorption band at 2164 nm due to C-H stretching vibration of the aromatic ring in the epoxy resin [16]. The epoxy conversion is given by [19]:

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{\left[\frac{A_{EP,t}}{A_{CH,t}} \right]}{\left[\frac{A_{EP,0}}{A_{CH,0}} \right]} \quad (1)$$

where α is the conversion, $A_{CH,0}$ and $A_{CH,t}$ refer to the areas of the “inert” reference peak at the start of the reaction ($t=0$) and after time, t , respectively. $A_{EP,0}$ and $A_{EP,t}$ are the areas of the epoxy peak for the uncured and partially cured resin at a specified time, respectively.

Figure 4(a) shows the degree of conversion for the epoxy functional group using conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy at specified isothermal conditions. In Figure 4(b), the data for conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy at 60 °C have been cross-plotted with data obtained using the multi-functional sensor configuration (secondary cavity). Although the sensor configuration has not been optimised, the quality of the spectra is adequate to extract cure kinetic data. From Figure 4(b), it is readily apparent that the data obtained from the multi-functional sensor and conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy are similar.

Figure 4 (a) Plot of the degree of conversion of the epoxy functional group as a function of cure-time using conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy at 60 °C. (b) Comparison of the degree of conversion of the epoxy functional group obtained using the multi-functional sensor and conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy at 60 °C.

Strain and Temperature Monitoring During Cure (Primary Fabry-Perot Cavity and FBG Sensor)

The primary Fabry-Perot cavity length, d , can be determined from the interference fringe separation across a spectral width of $\Delta\lambda$ using the equation [20]:

$$\text{Cavity length } (\mu m) = \frac{n \lambda_1 \lambda_2}{2000 (\Delta \lambda)} \quad (2)$$

where λ_1, λ_2 (nm) are wavelengths corresponding to the maxima of fringes that are separated in phase by $2n\pi$ where 'n' is an integer. The longitudinal strain, ϵ , in the EFPI sensor of gauge length, L , due to a cavity length change of Δd can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\Delta d}{L} \quad (3)$$

With reference to the FBG sensor in the primary EFPI sensor (isolated from strain), the temperature-induced shift, $\Delta\lambda_B$, in Bragg resonance wavelength, λ_B , can be expressed as [21]:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = \lambda_B (\alpha_n + \alpha_\Lambda) \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where ΔT is the temperature change, α_n is the thermo-optic coefficient and α_Λ is the thermal expansion coefficient of the fibre.

As shown in Figure 1, the Bragg grating that was inscribed in the primary optical fibre is in a strain-free condition and therefore any shift in the Bragg reflection corresponds to a change in the temperature. The spectral response of the primary Fabry-Perot (FP) cavity and the Bragg grating at the start and end of the cross-linking reaction at room temperature is shown in Figure 5(a). The overlapped signal of distinctive Bragg reflection and the transfer function of the FP cavity are readily visible.

The Bragg reflection peak shift of 0.3 nm towards a longer wavelength was observed when the temperature of the resin was raised by 34.6 °C to the isothermal cure temperature of 60 °C. This shift was found to be in good agreement with the Ge-B co-doped Bragg grating temperature sensitivity of 8.59 pm°C⁻¹ reported by Pal *et al.* [22]. The Bragg reflection peak was restored to its initial value of 1539.54 nm when the cured resin was cooled back to the room temperature. This demonstrates that the Bragg grating was maintained in a strain-free state during the cross-linking reaction.

Figures 5(a) Response of EFPI/FBG sensor before and after cross-linking and (b) comparison of degree of conversion based on secondary Fresnel-based sensor and conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy.

The separation of the FP interference fringes as shown in Figure 5(a) was a result of the change in the primary FP cavity length. The cavity lengths corresponding to the pre- and post-cure state of the resin, calculated using Equation 2, were found to be 161 μm and 156 μm respectively. The displacement of the fringes caused by shrinkage-induced longitudinal compressive strain is readily apparent from Figure 5(a). The superposed Bragg signal was seen to return to its original value at when the sample was cooled back to room temperature. The influence of cross-talk on the sensor response and decoupling of measurands is being investigated.

Qualitative Cross-linking Monitoring: The intensity of the reflected light from a pair of cleaved optical fibres (distal ends of a 2 x 2 coupler) was used as a secondary sensor to infer the changes in the refractive index of the resin during cross-linking. These fibres were mounted on the primary optical fibre as described previously. The cleaved optical fibres were positioned 5 mm from the reflective coating on the end-face of the capillary.

The Fresnel signal was monitored as a function of cross-linking and the reflected signal from two secondary fibres was directed using the FTIR spectrometer. The FTIR was operated at a resolution of 0.025 nm and 64 scans. The intensity of the reflected light (Fresnel signal) was monitored via the amplitude of the interferogram. This demonstrates that the multi-functional sensor (using one or more of the secondary fibres) can be used to infer the refractive index during cross-linking of the resin. Figure 5(b) shows the data obtained from the Fresnel sensors and the depletion of the epoxy during the cross-linking reaction follows a similar trend.

In the case of the Fresnel sensor data, the amplitude of the interferogram signal is a function of the refractive index contrast between the core of the fibre and the cross-linking resin; the initial decrease in the amplitude of the Fresnel sensor can be attributed to a decrease in the refractive index as the resin is heated from ambient to 60 °C. The gradual increase in the reflected light intensity can be attributed to the increase in the molecular weight during the cross-linking reaction at 60 °C. The stabilisation of the reflected light intensity implies a retardation of the rate of cross-linking. This intensity-based sensor system can be used to obtain qualitative information on the rate of heating, cross-linking rate and monitor when the cross-linking reaction reaches a steady state at a particular isothermal cross-linking temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of using the multi-functional sensor design for simultaneous measurement of strain, temperature, chemical concentration and Fresnel reflection during the cross-linking of a thermosetting resin system has been demonstrated. A conventional FTIR spectrometer was used to interrogate the various parameters.

Primary EFPI/FBG sensor response to temperature and strain was characterized in detail using separate EFPI and FBG sensors. The feasibility of using the FTIR spectrometer to interrogate the primary Fabry-Perot cavity and the fibre Bragg grating was also demonstrated.

Good correlation was observed for degree of conversion obtained from the secondary chemical sensor attached to the multi-functional sensor, and conventional transmission FTIR spectroscopy experiments. Good correlation was also observed between the Fresnel-based secondary sensor results that were monitored via the spectrometer.

This sensor system is ideal to study chemical and physical changes in engineering material and structures. The sensor system can be used for in-situ process monitoring as well as for in-service structural health monitoring. Once the composite has been processed, the sensor system(s) may also be used to monitor any degradation processes (chemical and/or physical) and thus bring the material out of service before catastrophic failure. This sensor design can also be used for gas sensing, evanescent wave spectroscopy, pH monitoring, etc.

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